

Spectrophotometric Studies of Iron(III)-5,7, dibromo Oxine N-oxide complex

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Spectrophotometric studies of iron (III)-5,7,dibromo oxine N-oxide complex have been carried out and the presence of at least two complexes (1:1; 1:2) is reported. Comparative studies of iron (III)-oxine N-oxide indicate that the equilibrium constant for the 1:2 complex in the case of 5,7,dibromo oxine N-oxide is higher than that in the case of 1:1 iron (III)-oxine N-oxide complex. The reagent, however does not offer any advantage over oxine N-oxide as a spectrophotometric reagent for iron and is, in fact inferior in many respects to most of the well-known and commonly used colorimetric reagents for iron.

5,7-Dibromo oxine N-oxide has recently been used for the spectrophotometric determination of uranium (VI)¹. Bhat and Jain² studied iron (III)-oxine-N-oxide complex spectrophotometrically and reported the existence of a 1:1 complex within the pH range of 0.5 and 1.5. The iron (III) complex produced by oxine-N-oxide has also been reported to be less stable than that produced by oxine³. The present investigation on iron (III)-5,7-dibromo oxine-N-oxide was undertaken with a view to carry out the comparative study in relation to the complex produced by oxine-N-oxide, and to ascertain whether this reagent had any analytical advantages over oxine N-oxide.

An ethanolic solution of 5,7-dibromo oxine N-oxide produces a deep brownish black water soluble complex with iron (III) salts and spectrophotometric studies on this complex are described in this paper.

EXPERIMENTAL

Reagents and apparatus: 5,7-dibromo oxine N-oxide was prepared by the method described by Bhat *et al.*¹. An ethanolic solution ($1 \times 10^{-3}M$) of the reagent was used. Standard solution of iron (III)- perchlorate was prepared by oxidising a solution of ferrous ammonium sulphate (Analar BDH), containing 55.85 mg of iron with alkaline hydrogen peroxide. The resultant ferric hydroxide (free from H_2O_2) was dissolved in warm perchloric acid and the solution so obtained was diluted to 500 ml. The strength of this solution was $2.0 \times 10^{-3}M$.

Spectrophotometric measurements were made using Unicam spectrophotometer model SP 600. pH measurements were made with the help of a Beckman pH meter model H2 using a suitable glass electrode.

1. Bhat, A. N., Gupta, R. D. and Jain, B. D., *This Journal* (under publication).
2. Bhat, A. N. and Jain B. D., *J. Sci. Ind. Res. (India)* 1960, 19B, 295.

Absorption Spectra: An ethanolic solution of 5,7-dibromo oxine *N*-oxide ($1.25 \times 10^{-4}M$) showed an absorption maximum at 383 m μ while that of oxine *N*-oxide at 365 m μ . The absorption spectra of iron (III)-5,7-dibromo oxine *N*-oxide complex of strength $2 \times 10^{-4}M$ with respect to iron and having a molar concentration ratio of the reagent to metal varying from 1 to 4 was found to have three absorption maxima at 420-30 m μ , 500 m μ and 625-50 m μ , the strongest absorption being at 420 m μ (Fig. 1). The absorption due to the reagent at this wave length being negligible, all subsequent studies were carried out at 420 m μ . The absorption spectra of the complexes were also studied at pH 2.6-3.6 and in each case three peaks were observed at the above wave lengths.

The absorption spectra of iron (III)-oxine *N*-oxide complex formed when the strength of iron was kept the same as above and the concentration ratio of the reagent to metal ion varied from 1 to 4 were also taken. Under these conditions the absorption peaks were observed at 400, 500 and 650 m μ (Fig. 2), the strongest absorption being at 500 m μ . The absorption due to iron (III)-5,7-dibromo oxine *N*-oxide at 420-30 m μ is much stronger than that of iron (III)-oxine *N*-oxide complex of the same strength with reference to iron (III).

FIG. 1. Absorption Spectra of iron (III)-5,7-dibromo oxine *N*-oxide complex.

FIG. 2.

Minimum amount of the reagent necessary: The optical density at 420 m μ of a series of solution containing 5,7-dibromo oxine *N*-oxide and iron (III) in the molar ratio of 1:1 to 10:1 and at pH 3.6 were determined. The results plotted in Fig. 3 show that the portion of the curve after A i.e., when the molar ratio is more than 8, is a straight line. For the determination of iron, however, the reagent to iron ratio was maintained at 10 in the subsequent studies as the excess of the reagent had no effect on the optical density of the complex.

Effect of pH: The effect of pH on iron (III)-5,7-dibromo oxine *N*-oxide complex of strength $2 \times 10^{-3}M$ with respect to iron and having a molar ratio of reagent to metal as 10:1 was studied and it was found that the optical density increased as the pH of the complex was raised as indicated below:

pH	2.4	3.0	3.4	3.7	4.0	4.5
Optical density	0.036	0.056	0.072	0.085	0.099	0.125

Effect of pH beyond 4.5 on the complex could not be studied in the above solution due to the appearance of opalescence at higher pH. Hence the subsequent studies were carried out at a lower pH (3.6).

The colour of the complex was stable for 72 hr. at 15° - $40^{\circ}C$ and the complex was found to obey Lambert Beer's law at 420 m μ in the concentration range of 0.22 to 3.08 ppm of iron (III) in solution.

FIG. 3.

FIG. 4. x ml of p molar 5,7-dibromo oxine *N*-oxide added to $(10-x)$ ml of p molar Iron (III) perchlorate solution ($p = 1 \times 10^{-3}$; 0.66×10^{-3} and 0.5×10^{-3})

Molar composition of the complex: Job's method of continuous variations³ as modified by Vosburgh and Cooper⁴ was employed for determining the molar composition of the complex. Optical densities of the following three sets of solutions prepared by mixing (a) x ml. of $1 \times 10^{-3}M$ 5,7 dibromo oxine *N*-oxide solution with $(10-x)$ ml of $1 \times 10^{-3}M$ iron (III) solution, (b) x ml of $0.5 \times 10^{-3}M$ of reagent solution with $(10-x)$ ml of $0.5 \times 10^{-3}M$ iron (III) solution and (c) x ml. of $0.666 \times 10^{-3}M$ of reagent with $(10-x)$ ml of $0.666 \times 10^{-3}M$ of iron (III) solution (where x varied from 1 to 9) were determined at 420 m μ , 500 m μ and 650 m μ employing 5,7, dibromo oxine *N*-oxide solution of the corres-

3. Job, P., *Ann. Chim.*, 1928, 9(10), 113.

4. Vosburgh, W. C. and Cooper, G.R., *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1941, 63, 437.

ponding strength as reference solution. The function y , defined as the difference between the optical density observed for a given mixture of the constituents and the corresponding optical densities of the respective components for no reaction, was taken in the present case as observed optical density. The values of y are plotted against x in each case in Fig. 4, in which the peaks in curves occur when the molar ratio of iron (III) to 5,7-dibromo oxine *N*-oxide is approximately 1:2 at 420 $m\mu$ and 1:1 at 500 $m\mu$ and 650 $m\mu$. The above observations indicate the formation of two complexes in the case of 5,7-dibromo oxine *N*-oxide. The presence of a 1:2 complex was further verified using Asmus' straight line method⁵ (Fig 5).

FIG. 5.

On the basis of molar composition of the above complexes the following tentative structures are suggested.

The molar composition of iron (III) oxine *N*-oxide complex was also determined by Job's method at 400, 500 and 650 $m\mu$, and in each case the molar composition was found to be 1:1.

Interference due to foreign ions: The ratio of the molar concentration of 5,7-dibromo oxine *N*-oxide to iron was 10 in the stock solution of the complex and its strength was 1×10^{-4} with respect to iron (III). Three ml. of this solution was taken and mixed with a known amount of a solution of the foreign salt and the total volume made upto 12.5 ml mark in a flask in each case with aqueous ethanol maintaining the alcoholic strength at 50 per cent in order to keep the reagent in solution. The optical density of this solution was determined at 420 m μ employing 5,7-dibromo oxine *N*-oxide of the corresponding strength as reference solution. The concentration of the foreign salt in the complex was progressively increased till the difference in the percentage transmission from the theoretical value was 2. Thus the limits of the interference of various cations and anions were determined and found to be manganese (20 ppm), cadmium (20 ppm), nickel (8 ppm), zinc (10 ppm), cobalt (12 ppm), vanadium (1 ppm), tartrate (2 ppm), citrate (1 ppm), phosphate, oxalate, tungstate, molybdate, uranium (VI), cerium (IV) ions interfered even when present in very small concentrations (1 ppm).

Determination of equilibrium constant: Determination of equilibrium constant of iron (III)-5,7-dibromo oxine *N*-oxide complex was carried out by the method of Harvey and Manning⁶. The spectrophotometric measurements for this purpose were done at 420 m μ and at a pH 3.6. The value of log K was found to be 6.9 at 20°C.

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6. Harvey, A. E. and Manning, D. L., *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1950, 72, 4488.